

Radiotherapy Evolutionary Algorithm Further 2d Pareto-Multi Objective Optimization with Biological Effective Model for Head-Neck Cancer Hyperfractionated Treatment

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online : 29 April 2023</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Dr F Casesnoves PhD</p>	<p>Constrained algorithms for BED model (Biological Effective Dose) in Head and Neck tumors Hyperfractionated TPO optimized with Pareto-Multiobjective (PMO) Genetic Algorithms (GA) software are obtained. The mathematical method for constrained GA is applied for a number of series of Pareto Functions. Results demonstrate PMO-AI imaging process sequences and extensive numerical values of PMO Head and Neck cancer parameters. Comparison and review with simple constrained GA Optimization is presented. Improved RT Head and Neck cancer TPO, and tumors in general for Fractional-dose photon dose delivery are explained in brief.</p>

KEYWORDS: Pareto-Multiobjective Optimization (PMO), Mathematical Methods (MM), Biological Models (BM), Radiation Therapy (RT), Initial Tumor Clonogenes Number Population (N_0), Effective Tumor Population Clonogenes Number ($N_{Effective}$), Linear Quadratic Model (LQM), Integral Equation (IE), Tumor Control Probability (TCP), Normal Tissue Complications Probability (NTCP), Biological Effective model (BED), Tumor Control Cumulative Probability (TCCP), Radiation Photon-Dose (RPD), Nonlinear Optimization, Radiotherapy Treatment Planning Optimization (TPO), Source-Surface Distance (SSD), Software Engineering Methods, Radiation Photon-Dose, Attenuation Exponential Factor (AEF), Nonlinear Optimization, Radiotherapy Wedge Filter (WF), Anisotropic Analytic Model (AAA), Fluence Factor (FF), Omega Factor (OF), Treatment Planning Optimization (TPO), Breast Tumor (BT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Pareto-Multiobjective Optimization (PMO), Genetic Algorithms (GA).

I. INTRODUCTION

The objective of the contribution is apply Artificial Intelligence with Constrained Genetic Algorithms on radiotherapy BED model for Head and Neck tumors [87,88].

Nonlinear GA-PMO engineering software was improved with matrix algebra constraints and designed in programs/patterns for PMO-BED models. A review of previous research with additional numerical results for two types of selected simple-constrained BED model parameters is supplemented. Thorough GA hyperfractionated radiotherapy TPO findings are presented both in 2D graphics and dataset. The matrix-algebra constraints and the extensive comparison among several parameters selection constitutes the innovation of the study. At 2D graphics, Pareto Optimal choice is sharply indicated.

In brief, a constrained extension of previous Nonlinear Pareto-Multiobjective GA optimization was performed for radiotherapy BED models in Head and Neck tumors [87,88]. Applications for radiotherapy TPO and future improvements in RT are explained in short.

II. MATHEMATICAL AND COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

The Pareto-Multiobjective Optimization foundation BED_{Effective} model was set in software, [24,88]. Parameters intervals are detailed in Tables 1-3. Algorithms 1-2 and Equation 1 set the formulas and constraints [85-88]. Two different PMO optimization programming series are presented with different parameter intervals magnitudes, Tables 1-3. This BED model constitutes the fundamentals

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for fractionate radiotherapy, although there are variations among authors [20-25]. Formulation is based on previous studies computational software [1-21,85-88]. The algorithm that was set, with Chebyshev L_1 norm, [Algorithm 1], reads,

The general 2D Pareto-Multiobjective problem, [Algorithm-1] with inequality constraints, either linear or nonlinear, reads,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Minimize,} \\ & F(\vec{x}) = (f_1(\vec{x}), f_2(\vec{x}), \dots, f_N(\vec{x})), \\ & \text{subject to,} \\ & K_i(\vec{x}) \geq 0, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, M \end{aligned}$$

(Algorithm 1)

where

$F(x)$: Main function to be optimized.

$f_i(x)$: Every function of same variables (x).

$K_i(x)$: Constraints functions such as in general $N \neq M$.

BED model has been adapted on the difficulty to obtain an stable and reliable T_{Pot} magnitude. PMO in Head and Neck, [24,88] tumors simplest BED model reads,

Chebyshev L_1 Optimization for,

$$\begin{aligned} BED_{Effective} = & kd \left[1 + \frac{d \times \beta}{\alpha} \right] - \dots \\ & \dots - \frac{\ln(2)}{\alpha} \left[\frac{T_{Treatment} - T_{Delay}}{T_{Potential}} \right]; \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where

k : Dose fraction number for hyperfractionated RT protocol. [20-25].

Software pattern set [35, 45] Fractions.

d : Dose fraction for hyperfractionated RT protocol. [20-25].

Software pattern set [1, 2.2] Gy.

α : Clonogen Head and Neck tumor radiosensitivity parameter [0.19, 0.61]. [20-25].

β : Clonogen Head and Neck tumor radiosensitivity parameter [0.0581]. [20-25].

$T_{Treatment}$: Total time for radiation dose delivered. Software pattern set [22, 55] days. [20-25].

T_{Delay} : Total standard repopulation delays for RT. Software set [21] days. [20-25].

$T_{Potential}$: Total standard Head and Neck cancer potential repopulation factor.

Software pattern set [3.5, 4.5] days. [20-25].

Equation 1 [developed for software patterns, Casesnoves, 2022, based on classical author' BED model, mainly Fowler] .-Head and Neck PMO algorithm [1-21,85-88] implemented in software. The intervals for optimization parameters in software are detailed. It is an improvement from a series of previous research in radiotherapy.

During programming trials it was found that precision was increased by using algebraic constraints in main patterns. Therefore, the constraints algebraic algorithm developed for Pareto-Multiobjective problem, [Algorithm-2, Casesnoves 2023] reads,

Constraints,
For Pareto Functions $i = 1, 2$,
and lower – upper limits of
optimization parameters,

$$S_{Lower} \leq K_i + d_i + T_{(Treatment)_i} \leq S_{Upper},$$

(Algorithm 2)

where

S_{LOWER} : Summatory of all lower constraints for parameters [K, d, T].

S_{UPPER} : Summatory of all upper constraints for parameters [K, d, T].

K_i : Dose fraction number parameter for [$i = 1, 2$].

d_i : Dose fraction magnitude parameter for [$i = 1, 2$].

$T_{TREATMENT}$: Treatment time magnitude parameter for [$i = 1, 2$].

The programming method(s) applied for this research are based on previous papers [1-20,24,74,88]. For GA-PMO modeling, Equation 1 and Algorithms 1-2 are implemented on 2D programs. However, Algorithm 2 was programmed with constraints functions. Table 1 shows Constrained GA Optimization selected parameters according to Algorithm 2. Tables 2-3 show the 2D GA-PMO simple programming method variations to obtain acceptable better calculations, and 2D Graphical Optimization processing images, error determinations, and get good approximations for the PMO-BED model. For simple simulations, the difference between the first and second simulations is given by Dose Fraction and Dose Interval parameters, Tables 2-3.

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CONSTRAINED GENETIC ALGORITHM OPTIMIZATION PARAMETER INTERVAL FOR HEAD AND NECK TUMOR ALGORITHM 2 [References at Tables 2-3]	
Parameter	Magnitude Interval
Constraints Interval Algorithm 2	[77.0 , -56.0] [Note that there are two linear inequality constraints in matrix]
Dose Fraction Number	[25 , 35]
Dose Fraction Magnitude	[1 , 2] Gy
T _{Treatment}	[30 , 40] Days
T _{Delay}	21 Days
T _{Potential}	[3.5 , 4.5]
α [Gy ⁻¹] β [Gy ⁻²] Parameters	[0.19 , 0.61] Gy ⁻¹ [0.0581] Gy ⁻² fixed
Dose Interval in Objective Function	45 Gy for Pareto F 1 function 55 Gy for Pareto F 2 function

Table 1.-Matlab Constrained GA optimization dataset. Note the values of Matlab constraints matrix in Algorithm 2. In Matlab and other similar systems, the constraints can be set as a matrix equation. As in Tables 2-3, the simulations were done with approximate numerical-experimental data from several authors. T_{Potential} in Head and Neck cancer is about 4 days as average. Simulation dataset from [20-25,74,75,80,81,85-88] .

GENETIC ALGORITHM ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE OPTIMIZATION PARAMETER INTERVAL FOR HEAD AND NECK TUMORS SECOND GA OPTIMIZATION		
PARAMETER	MAGNITUDE INTERVAL	ADDITIONAL
Dose fraction number	[35, 50]	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-88].
Dose fraction magnitude	[1.2 , 2.0] Gy	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-88]. Set with intervals according to different criteria.
T _{Treatment} (total)	[22,52] Days	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-88]. Set with intervals according to different criteria. The RT treatment varies according to weekends breaks, secondary effects, patient circumstances, etc.
T _{Delay}	[20,30] Days	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-88]. Set with intervals according to different criteria.
T _{Potential}	[3.5, 4.5] Days	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-88]. Set with intervals according to different criteria.
α [Gy ⁻¹] , β [Gy ⁻²] radiobiological parameters	[calculated from head and neck cancer experimental α = 0.40 ±0.21 Gy ⁻¹ , β= 0.0581 Gy ⁻²]	
Dose interval in Objective Function	35 Gy for Pareto F 1 function 50 Gy for Pareto F 2 function	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-88]. Set with two total dose Pareto Functions according to different criteria.

Table 3.-The second simulations were done with approximate numerical-experimental data from several authors. T_{Potential} is taken [3.5, 4.5] days.

III. OPTIMIZATION GRAPHICAL RESULTS

2D Graphical results for first constrained optimization are shown in Figures 1-2. The simple constrained optimization results are presented in Figures 3-7. In general, constrained optimization with algorithm 2 shows be better than simple constrained one. However, differences are not very high.

Algebraic constrained Model Results

GENETIC ALGORITHM ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE OPTIMIZATION PARAMETER INTERVAL FOR HEAD AND NECK TUMORS FIRST GA OPTIMIZATION		
PARAMETER	MAGNITUDE INTERVAL	ADDITIONAL
Dose fraction number	[32, 40]	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-86].
Dose fraction magnitude	[1.2,1.5] Gy	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-86]. Set with intervals according to different criteria.
T _{Treatment} (total)	[22,52] Days	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-86]. Set with intervals according to different criteria. The RT treatment varies according to weekends breaks, secondary effects, patient circumstances, etc.
T _{Delay}	[20,30] Days	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-86]. Set with intervals according to different criteria.
T _{Potential}	[3.5, 4.5] Days	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-86]. Set with intervals according to different criteria.
α [Gy ⁻¹] , β [Gy ⁻²] radiobiological parameters	[calculated from head and neck cancer experimental α = 0.40 ±0.21 Gy ⁻¹ , β= 0.0581 Gy ⁻²]	
Dose interval in Objective Function	47 Gy for Pareto F 1 function 55 Gy for Pareto F 2 function	Usual protocol in literature [1-21,74-86]. Set with two total dose Pareto Functions according to different criteria.

Table 2.-First GA optimization dataset. The simulations were done with approximate numerical-experimental data from several authors. T_{Potential} in head and neck cancer is about 4 days as average. Simulation dataset from [20-25,74,75,80,81,85-88] .

Figure 1.-Constrained optimization Multifunctional GA 2D graph (100 generations). This is the most important graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy. The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f 1 and f 2 show low residuals. Therefore, results are acceptable in first optimization for function 1 and function 2 . Enhanced in Appendix.

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Figure 2.-Constrained optimization Multifunctional GA 2D graph (100 generations). This is the most important graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy. The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f 1 and f 2 show low residuals.

Review Simple Constrained 2D Simulations Model Results

Figures 3-7 show PMO results. Tables 4-6 present details of both numerical PMO optimization results. Table 4 shows the constrained optimization results (100 generations, optimal fraction dose ($d \in [1.6, 1.7]$ Gy). The most important to validate the results are those ones that show the Pareto Front. Average distance among generation individuals, stopping criteria, are also important. The other details are complementary and shown in additional 2D charts for first and second PMO optimization. For simple constrained optimization maximum number of generations selected was 300-800. Score histograms also prove the validity of the software and PMO done. Running time for both processes is about 2-4 minutes. Numerical results, Tables 5-6, resume for PMO in simple constrained optimization BED model. For this simple constrained optimization dose fraction magnitude should be less than 2 Gy approximately [19-21,75,85-88].

Review PMO-GA 2D Imaging Processing First Simple Constrained Optimization Results

First optimization results are shown in Figures 3-4, Table 5. Pareto function 2 results are more accurate than Pareto function 1. Every chart of Artificial Intelligence GA is detailed with further explanations.

Figure 3.-First optimization Multifunctional GA 2D graph. This is the most important graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy. The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f 1 and f 2 show low residuals. Therefore, results are acceptable in first optimization for function 1 and function 2 . The number of points on the Pareto front was: 18. The number of generations was : 300.

Figure 4.-First optimization Multifunctional GA 2D graph. This is the complementary multifunctional graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy. The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f 1 and f 2 show low residuals. Therefore, results are acceptable in first optimization for function 1 and function 2 The number of points on the Pareto front was: 18. The number of generations was : 300.

Review PMO-GA 2D Imaging Processing Second Simple Constrained Optimization Results

Second optimization results are shown in Figures 5-7, Table 6. Pareto function 2 results be more accurate than pareto function 1. Every chart of Artificial Intelligence GA is detailed with further explanations.

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Figure 5.-Second simulation. Multifunctional GA 2D graph. This is the most important graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy.

The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f 1 and f 2 show low residuals. Therefore, results are acceptable. The number of points on the Pareto front was: 18. The number of generations was : 300.

Figure 6.-This is the most important graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy.

The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f1 and f2 show low residuals. Objective 2 is more accomplished. Therefore, results are acceptable. The number of points on the Pareto front was: 18. The number of generations was : 300. Enhanced in Appendix.

Figure 7.-This is important complementary graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy.

Average Distances is a significant parameter. The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f 1 and f 2 show low average distances, less than 2. Therefore, results are acceptable. The number of points on the Pareto front was: 18. The number of generations was : 300.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Constrained optimization numerical data is shown in Table 4. Large numbers for simple constrained optimization are shown in Tables 5-6.

Numerical Results Constrained Optimization

Constrained optimization show be acceptable within numerical intervals, Table 4.

Table 4. Constrained Optimization Algorithm 2 numerical results.

HEAD AND NECK HYPOFRACTIONATED NUMERICAL RESULTS FOR CONSTRAINED OPTIMIZATION FOR ALGORITHM 2		
Parameter/Settings	Magnitude Interval	Additional
Generations	150	Not too big figure
Pareto-Distance	$\approx 10^{-2}$	Acceptable precision
K	$\approx [27 , 34]$	Within literature data
d	$\approx [1.6 , 1.7]$	Within literature data
T _{treatment}	$\approx [30 , 35]$	Within literature data

Numerical Results Simple Constrained Optimization Review

PMO-GA Numerical Results

Examples of Numerical results resume for PMO in BED model are detailed in Tables 5-6. Chebyshev norms were set for [55 , 65] Gy interval. Dose fraction magnitude should be less than 2 Gy approximately. Numerical Results for model are developed and reviewed from the innovation from [20,21,75,85-88].

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EN. And based on ‘The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity’. Revised Edition. ALLEA. 2017. This research was completely done by the author, the computational-software, calculations, images, mathematical propositions and statements, reference citations, and text is original for the author. When a mathematical statement, algorithm, proposition or theorem is presented, demonstration is always included. If any results inconsistency is found after publication, it is clarified in subsequent contributions. When a citation such as [Casesnoves, ‘year’] is set, it is exclusively to clarify intellectual property at current times, without intention to brag. The article is exclusively scientific, without any commercial, institutional, academic, religious, religious-similar, non-scientific theories, personal opinions, political ideas, or economical influences. When anything is taken from a source, it is adequately recognized. Ideas and some text expressions/sentences from previous publications were emphasized due to a clarification aim [38, 43-44].

VII. SCIENTIFIC ETHIC STANDARDS

GA-AI RT applications methods from these publications were created by Dr Casesnoves in 2022. 2D/3D Graphical Optimization Methods were created by Dr Francisco Casesnoves in 3rd November 2016, and Interior Optimization Methods in 2019. BED model setting in Algorithms and programming were developed by Dr Casesnoves from previously published BED models. This article has previous papers information, from [1-10], whose inclusion is essential to make the contribution understandable. This study was carried out, and their contents are done according to the International Scientific Community and European Union Technology and Science Ethics [38-41]. References [38,43,44]: ‘European Textbook on Ethics in Research’. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research. Unit L3. Governance and Ethics. European Research Area. Science and Society. EUR 24452

APPENDIX

Figure 1. (Enhanced) .-Constrained optimization Multifunctional GA 2D graph (100 generations). This is the most important graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy. The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f 1 and f 2 show low residuals. Therefore, results are acceptable in first optimization for function 1 and function 2.

Figure 6. (Enhanced).-This is the most important graph given by software when PMO is performed to check the optimization accuracy. The fundamentals of Nonlinear PMO calculations are usually based on 2D PMO functions charts. In this study both f1 and f2 show low residuals. Objective 2 is more accomplished. Therefore, results are acceptable. The number of points on the Pareto front was: 18. The number of generations was : 300.